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Participation in Cultural Events in the Italian Regions

It decreased on average by 8.86% between 2005 and 2020

Istat BES calculates the value of "Cultural Participation Outside the Home". This is a variable that considers the percentage of people over six who have practiced two or more cultural activities in the 12 months preceding the interview out of the total of people aged six and over. For cultural activities we consider: theater, museums and / or exhibitions, archaeological sites, monuments, concerts of ranking music, opera, concerts of other music.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of cultural participation outside the home. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place for the value of cultural participation away from home in 2020 equal to an amount of 39.60 units, followed by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 37.40 units, and by Lazio with a value of 37.20 units. In the middle of the table there are Veneto with a value of 33.00 units, followed by Liguria with an amount of 32.90 units, and Umbria with a value of 28.60 units. Molise closes the ranking with an amount of 22.50 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 22.00 units, and Calabria with an amount of 15.90 units. On average, the value of cultural participation outside the home was equal to an amount of 29.83 units in 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in cultural participation outside the home in the period between 2005 and 2020. Liguria is in first place by value of the percentage change in cultural participation outside the home between 2005 and 2020 with an amount equal to 16,67% equal to an amount of 4.70 units, Valle d'Aosta is in second place for a value of 5.30% equal to an amount of 1.70 units, and Tuscany with an amount of 0.29% equal to an amount of 0.10 units. In the middle of the table there are Molise with an amount of -7.79% equal to an amount of -1.90 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of -10.20% equal to an amount of -4,50 units, and from Basilicata with an amount of -10.33% equal to an amount of -2.80 units. Abruzzo closes the ranking with an amount of -15.98% equal to an amount of -5.40 units, followed by the Marche with a value of -24.23% equal to an amount of -8.60 units and Calabria with a value of -36.65% equal to an amount of -9.20 units. Overall, in the period between 2005 and 2020 the total value equal to an amount of -8.86% equal to an amount of -2.84 units.

Italian Macro-Regions. If we consider the Italian macro-regions, we can verify that the value of participation in cultural events outside the home has decreased both overall in Italy and in the North, South and Center. Looking at the trend of the historical series, it appears that the value of participation in cultural events grew between 2005 and 2010-2011 and then subsequently decreased, reaching the minimum values in 2020. This fluctuating trend can be somehow reconnected to the dimension of the global macro-economic structure. In fact, 2010-2011 is the period in which the financial crisis connected to subprime mortgages which began in the USA in 2007-2008 took full manifestation in Italy. Furthermore, the minimum value detected in 2020 can also be considered as a manifestation of the adversities related to the Covid pandemic. It follows that macro-economic events or financial crises and pandemics have significantly negative consequences in terms of the population's ability to participate in cultural events. Considering the case of the North, it appears that in 2005 37.70% of the population over the age of 6 took part in cultural events. This value increased in 2010 to a value of 39.60 units to reach a maximum peak in 2011 equal to an amount of 40.10 units. However, between

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2011 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events decreased from an amount of 40.10 units to a value of 34.80 units. If we consider the inter-periodical variations for Northern Italy it appears that in the period 2005-2020 the value of participation in cultural events decreased by 7.69% equal to an amount of -2.90 units, in the period between 2010 and 2022 this value decreased by -12.12% equal to an amount of -4.80 units, while between 2011 and 2020 this value decreased by 13.22% equal to an amount of -5.30 units. In 2020, just over a third of the population of the North took part in cultural events. A similar dynamic, with some marginal differences, can be found in Central Italy. In 2005, the value of participation in cultural events was equal to an amount of 36.50 units, reaching 40.20 units in 2010 and finally reaching the maximum in 2011 with a value of 40.60 units. However, between 2011 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events decreased to an amount of 34.50 units. It should be considered that participation in cultural events in Central Italy exceeded the corresponding value of the North in both 2010 and 2011 and then returned below the value of the North in 2020. Between 2015 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events in Central Italy it decreased by an amount equal to a value of -5.48% equal to an amount of -2.00 units, between 2010 and 2022 the value decreased by an amount of -14.18% equal to an amount of -5.70 units, while between 2011 and 2020 the value decreased by an amount equal to a value of -15.02% equal to a value of -6.10 units. In Southern Italy the value of participation in cultural events was equal to an amount of 27.00 units. Between 2005 and 2010 the value of participation in cultural events reached its periodic maximum with a value of 29.50 units, in 2011 this value was equal to an amount of 27.50 units, while in 2020 this value was equal to reach a minimum equal to a value of 23.30 units. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events decreased by an amount equal to a value of 13.70% equal to a value of -3.70 units, between 2010 and 2020 the value of participation in events cultural has decreased by a value equal to -21.02% equal to an amount of -6.20 units. Finally, between 2011 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events in Southern Italy decreased by an amount equal to -15.27% or by a value equal to -4.20 units. Overall, at the Italian level, the value of participation in cultural events in 2005 was equal to a value of 33.70 units. Between 2005 and 2010 this value reached a peak up to a value of 36.20 units, and then decreased to 35.80 units in 2011 and up to 30.80 units in 2020.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Sicily, Molise, Campania, Calabria, Basilicata, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Piedmont, Lazio, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta, Trentino-Alto Adige, Umbria, Marche, Liguria, Sardinia.

From the metric point of view, the value of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 23.7 units, while the value of Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 33.9 units. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, that is: $C2 = 33.9 > C1 = 23.7$. From a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that participation in cultural events outside the home is higher in the Center-North than in Southern Italy.

Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. A network analysis using the Manhattan distance is presented below. The analysis highlights the presence of two complex network structures, or consisting of more than two nodes, and two simplified network structures or consisting of only two nodes. There is a complex network structure between Lombardy, Veneto and Tuscany. Particularly:

- Lombardy has a connection with Veneto for a value of 0.87;

- Veneto has a connection with Lombardy for a value of 0.87 units and with Tuscany for a value of 0.89 units;
- Tuscany has a connection with Veneto for a value of 0.89 units.

There is a complex network structure between Liguria, Umbria and Marche, namely:

- Liguria has a connection with Umbria for a value of 0.81 units;
- Umbria has a connection with Liguria for a value of 0.81 units and with the Marche for a value of 0.95 units;
- Marche has a connection with Liguria for a value of 0,95.

There are two simplified network structures, namely:

- Molise and Sicily are connected with a link value of 0.8 units;
- Puglia and Campania are connected with a link value equal to a value of 0.81 units.

Machine Learning and Predictions. A comparison is made below between ten machine learning algorithms for predicting the future value of cultural participation in out-of-home events. The algorithms are compared in terms of performance through the minimization of statistical errors or MAE, MSE and RMSE and the maximization of R-Squared. The algorithms were trained with 80% of the available data. Through the application of these performance analysis criteria it is possible to identify the following ranking of the algorithms, namely:

- SGD and Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 7;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 11;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 15;
- kNN with a payoff value of 20;
- Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- SVM-Support Vector Machine with a payoff value of 28;
- Constant with a payoff value of 32;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

The SGD algorithm is chosen for the prediction. It appears that there are regions for which the algorithm predicts an increasing trend in the value of participation in cultural events outside the home, namely:

- Calabria with a variation from an amount of 15.90 units up to a value of 19.81 units or equal to a value of 3.91 units equal to a value of 24.57%;
- Marche with a variation from an amount of 26.90 units up to a value of 29.92 units or a variation equal to an amount of 3.02 units equal to a value of 11.24%;
- Sardinia with a variation from an amount of 27.10 units up to a value of 30.14 units or equal to an amount of 3.04 units equal to a value of 11.21%;
- Umbria with a variation from an amount of 28.60 units up to a value of 31.11 units or equal to a value of 2.51 units equal to a value of 8.76%;
- Valle d'Aosta with a variation from an amount of 33.80 units up to a value of 36.21 units or equal to a value of 2.41 units equal to a value of 7.13%;
- Trentino-Alto Adige with a change from an amount of 39.60 units up to a value of 41.34 units or equal to an amount of 1.784 units equal to a value of 4.39%;

- Emilia Romagna with a variation from an amount of 34.50 units up to a value of 35.53 units or equal to an amount of 1.03 units equal to a value of 3.00%;
- Sicily with a variation from an amount of 22.00 units up to a value of 22.40 units or equal to a variation of 0.49 units equal to a value of 2.24%;
- Veneto with a variation from an amount of 33.00 units up to a value of 33.60 units equal to an amount of 0.60 units equal to a value of 1.81%.

In addition, there are regions for which the algorithm predicts a negative trend, namely:

- Lazio with a variation from an amount of 37.20 units up to a value of 37.01 units or equal to an amount of -0.19 units equal to a value of -0.52%;
- Basilicata with a variation from an amount of 37.20 units up to a value of 37.01 units or equal to a variation from an amount of -0.19 units equal to a value of -0.52%;
- Piedmont with a variation from an amount of 33.90 units up to a value of 33.00 units or equal to a value of -0.90 units or equal to a value of -2.66%;
- Lombardy with a variation from an amount of 35.50 units up to a value of 34.37 units or equal to a value of -1.13 units equal to a value of -3.17%;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a variation from an amount of 37.40 units up to a value of 35.65 units or equal to a variation of -1.75 units equal to a value of -4.68%;
- Campania with a variation from an amount of 23.70 units up to a value of 22.44 units or equal to a value of -1.26 units equal to a value of -5.32%;
- Tuscany with a variation from an amount of 34.70 units up to a value of 32.43 units or equal to a variation of -2.27 units equal to a value of -6.55%;
- Abruzzo with a variation from an amount of 28.40 units up to a value of 26.18 units or equal to a value of -2.22 units equal to a value of -7.80%;
- Liguria with a variation from a value of 32.90 units up to a value of 30.09 units or equal to an amount of -2.81 units equal to a value of -8.55%;
- Molise with a variation from an amount of 22.50 units up to a value of 20.45 units or equal to a variation of -2.05 units equal to a value of -9.11%.
- Puglia with a variation from an amount of 24.70 units up to a value of 20.72 units or equal to a variation of -3.98 units equal to an amount of -16.09%.

Conclusions. Between 2005 and 2020 the value of participation in cultural events decreased in all Italian macro-regions because of two macro-phenomena, namely the economic manifestation of the financial crisis of subprime mortgages and the crisis connected to the Covid-19 pandemic. There are only three regions in which the value of participation in cultural events has grown in the period between 2005 and 2020, i.e. Liguria with a + 16.67% equal to a value of 4.70 units., Valle d'Aosta with an amount of + 5.30% equal to a value of 1.70 units, and Tuscany with a + 0.29% equal to a value of 0.10 units. For all the other regions, the comparison between 2005 and 2020 in terms of participation in cultural events is significantly negative, with an overall average for the Italian regions equal to a value of -8.86% equal to an amount of -2, 84 units. The analysis of clustering shows that the regions of the Center-North have very high values of participation in cultural events, especially when considered in the light of the regions of Southern Italy. What appears evident is that the ability of Italians to participate in cultural events is strictly connected to the dimension of the economic cycle. In the presence of adverse macro-economic phenomena, Italians give up cultural events, inevitably creating a decline in the cultural entertainment sector. However, the data show the presence of a leading role in Central Italy, in fact in the periods of growth in participation in cultural events between 2005 and the two-year period 2010-2011 Central Italy performed better than Northern Italy, and then returned to a value at below the North in 2020. It follows that Central Italy is the macro-

region with a pro-cyclical value, i.e. it grows much more than the average in the event of overall growth and tends to lose more in the event of a crisis in the sector compared with the other Italian macro-regions. From the analysis it is also possible to identify a trend in the added value produced by the cultural entertainment sector which obviously has a fluctuating trend characterized by income uncertainty, difficulty in organizing the production of added value, pro-cyclicity and excessive dependence on macro conditions - international economics. In this sense, it is necessary to create the conditions to make the sector anti-cyclical through bonuses and economic policies of culture that can allow continuity in the production of added value, especially in consideration of the positive effects in terms of externalities that the production of cultural events has for the population in the democratic regime.

	2020	Feature 1	Cluster	Silhouette
1	33.9	Piemonte	C2	0.684076
2	33.8	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2	0.67536
3	32.9	Liguria	C2	0.599099
4	35.5	Lombardia	C2	0.68905
5	39.6	Trentino-Alto A...	C2	0.657465
6	33.0	Veneto	C2	0.68632
7	37.4	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2	0.685842
8	34.5	Emilia-Romagna	C2	0.687525
9	34.7	Toscana	C2	0.680067
10	28.6	Umbria	C2	0.623945
11	26.9	Marche	C2	0.612007
12	37.2	Lazio	C2	0.681027
13	28.4	Abruzzo	C1	0.562714
14	22.5	Molise	C1	0.700935
15	23.7	Campania	C1	0.698348
16	24.7	Puglia	C1	0.702018
17	24.3	Basilicata	C1	0.685093
18	15.9	Calabria	C1	0.690783
19	22.0	Sicilia	C1	0.702308
20	27.1	Sardegna	C2	0.521897

	2020	Feature 1	SGD	KNN	Tree	Random Forest	Gradient Boosting	SVM	Neural Network	Linear Regression	AdaBoost	Constant	Fold
1	39,6	Trentino-Alto A...	41.3381	35.52	36.7	36.1134	37.0701	30.7314	68.451	42.7827	37.2	29.3158	15
2	34,5	Emilia-Romagna	35.5333	34.9	35.1	36.4543	35.6814	33.3519	28.2271	37.1126	34.7	29.5842	17
3	33,8	Valle d'Aosta/V...	36.2085	34.9	33.2667	34.4883	33.7132	32.6973	19.0738	41.7787	33.9	29.6211	4
4	37,4	Lazio	37.0066	34.86	38.5	36.2502	37.0428	33.1543	38.7331	57.1171	37.4	29.4421	7
5	37,4	Friuli-Venezia G...	35.6489	34.82	38.4	36.4561	36.0523	33.5695	33.5622	30.8319	35.5	29.4316	20
6	35,5	Lombardia	34.3741	34.7	38.0667	34.3763	35.8665	33.5972	28.785	37.3385	34.7	29.5316	8
7	33,0	Veneto	33.5978	34.48	34.9	34.3571	34.6417	34.0473	21.6347	20.454	34.7	29.6632	6
8	33,9	Piemonte	32.9985	34.3	38.0667	34.8605	34.2267	32.8589	19.9089	24.5098	33.8	29.6158	1
9	34,7	Toscana	32.4271	34.14	33.4	32.4621	33.4294	32.5439	17.4359	33.4081	33	29.5737	5
10	26,9	Marche	29.9226	31.44	28.0333	30.0675	28.6012	31.0966	4.99558	28.8404	28.6	29.9842	18
11	28,6	Umbria	31.1551	31.1	33.4	30.5429	29.4325	31.5008	6.43679	31.6401	32.9	29.8947	13
12	27,1	Sardegna	30.1388	30.3	27.9667	29.1807	29.3077	29.8928	4.24697	37.5725	28.6	29.9737	14
13	32,9	Liguria	30.0874	30.24	27.75	29.3833	27.7888	29.4297	4.81781	29.5946	28.4	29.6684	12
14	28,4	Abruzzo	26.1845	26.98	27.5333	24.9773	27.8024	26.8523	8.02125	22.3128	27.1	29.9053	16
15	24,3	Basilicata	23.7653	24.26	25.9	24.3143	25.2022	26.4039	17.6538	23.5747	24.7	30.1211	10
16	15,9	Calabria	19.8074	23.44	24.2333	23.5653	22.7595	27.4648	36.9202	23.5898	22.5	30.5632	2
17	22,0	Sicilia	22.4924	22.22	19.2	24.0694	22.8857	26.1896	23.4314	26.4056	23.7	30.2421	9
18	22,5	Molise	20.4503	22.12	18.95	24.0618	22.3106	26.2384	23.7245	9.43507	23.7	30.2158	11
19	23,7	Campania	22.4385	21.88	24.5	24.3053	24.6482	26.1016	20.5738	25.983	24.3	30.1526	19
20	24,7	Puglia	20.7248	21.68	23.5	22.2655	21.8201	26.227	24.0855	19.9928	22.5	30.1	3

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	35,7	36,1	39,4	35,7	38,5	37,7	38,6	36,2	30,6	36,4	38,5	37,4	36,2	36,9	36,3	33,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	32,1	34,6	40	40,7	36,9	40,3	38,6	38,2	33,8	33	37,6	37,5	33,1	35,7	36,4	33,8
Liguria	28,2	31,5	33	32,7	32	35,8	33,5	32,4	29,6	31,2	35,2	34,1	36	35,7	36,4	32,9
Lombardia	40,5	38,2	37,7	38,2	38,1	41,3	41,4	37,8	36,2	35	37,7	40,6	35,4	39,6	38,6	35,5
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	44,1	43,5	45,6	44,3	46,5	44,2	46,4	43,4	42	45,3	45,6	46,6	42,8	42,8	44,6	39,6
Veneto	37,2	37,7	35,2	38,9	36,5	38,3	40,1	37,7	35,3	32,2	35,5	37,3	35,9	38,3	38	33
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	37,9	34,2	38,3	41,7	41,2	43,1	42,3	38,6	36	37,7	41	42,7	38	39,9	38,4	37,4
Emilia-Romagna	36,4	39,5	39	37,4	37,1	38,5	39,1	36,3	34,5	35,4	37	39,8	41,2	41,3	40,8	34,5
Toscana	34,6	37,2	34,1	35	35,7	38,7	39,3	34,9	32,4	36	35,3	36,6	35,3	40,7	36,9	34,7
Umbria	32	33,7	32,7	30,8	32,7	33,2	34	34,2	30,7	32	36,3	36	35,8	37,1	34,8	28,6
Marche	35,5	33,2	31,8	31,8	34,6	34,4	36	31,4	31,1	30,7	34,5	35,9	35	31,6	34,2	26,9
Lazio	38,8	36,6	37,8	41,1	41,6	43,8	43,7	38,2	39,7	42,5	38,7	40,6	43,3	39,9	38,6	37,2
Abruzzo	33,8	30,6	30,7	31,7	30,4	36,4	33,9	28,2	27,3	26,4	27,6	28,4	29,2	27,9	31,8	28,4
Molise	24,4	25,6	24,9	26	27,3	26,4	26,2	26	20,7	24,4	24,6	27,3	26	25,1	24,2	22,5
Campania	27,9	26,6	27,7	25,7	28	28,2	25,4	24,4	22,5	21,9	26,1	26,2	26,2	26,1	30,9	23,7
Puglia	25,8	25,1	23,5	24,6	25,7	27,1	26,4	22,1	23,3	23,1	23,9	24,7	24,4	26,6	30,5	24,7
Basilicata	27,1	27,7	27,9	28,9	30,8	28,1	28,5	22,5	24,2	20,2	26,1	30,5	25,3	29,3	27,3	24,3
Calabria	25,1	22,5	20,6	23,7	24,4	26,5	24,9	21,4	17,7	19,4	21,1	20,3	20,9	23,6	23,3	15,9
Sicilia	24,7	24,1	23,8	25,8	27,6	30,5	26,9	25,9	20,5	22,5	27,4	25,7	23,2	25,7	26,2	22
Sardegna	31,5	30,9	32,5	34,5	32,8	35,4	37,6	28,7	25,3	33,2	28,3	32,4	32,6	30,1	34,5	27,1

Performance degli Algoritmi di Machine Learning

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
<i>SGD</i>	4,7173	2,1719	1,8582	0,8758
<i>Gradient Boosting</i>	5,3509	2,3132	1,6012	0,8591
<i>AdaBoost</i>	5,7355	2,3949	1,7550	0,8490
<i>Random Forest</i>	6,0712	2,4640	1,7030	0,8402
<i>kNN</i>	7,4562	2,7306	2,0540	0,8037
<i>Tree</i>	9,3935	3,0649	2,3683	0,7527
<i>SVM</i>	17,4370	4,1758	3,2788	0,5410
<i>Constant</i>	42,0888	6,4876	5,7053	-0,1080
<i>Linear Regression</i>	60,9432	7,8066	6,1524	-0,6044
<i>Neural Network</i>	248,5315	15,7649	12,7001	-5,5429

Partecipazione agli eventi culturali. Fonte: ISTAT BES

Macro-Regioni	Partecipazione ad Eventi Culturali				2005-2020		2010-2020		2011-2020	
	2005	2010	2011	2020	Var Ass	Var Per	Var Ass	Var Per	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	37,70	39,60	40,10	34,80	-2,90	-7,69	-4,80	-12,12	-5,30	-13,22
<i>Centro</i>	36,50	40,20	40,60	34,50	-2,00	-5,48	-5,70	-14,18	-6,10	-15,02
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	27,00	29,50	27,50	23,30	-3,70	-13,70	-6,20	-21,02	-4,20	-15,27
<i>Italia</i>	33,70	36,20	35,80	30,80	-2,90	-8,61	-5,40	-14,92	-5,00	-13,97

Rank	Regione	2020
1	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ 39,60
2	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 37,40
3	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 37,20
4	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 35,50
5	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 34,70
6	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 34,50
7	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 33,90
8	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 33,80
9	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 33,00
10	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 32,90
11	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 28,60
12	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 28,40
13	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 27,10
14	<i>Marche</i>	★ 26,90
15	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 24,70
16	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 24,30
17	<i>Campania</i>	★ 23,70
18	<i>Molise</i>	★ 22,50
19	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 22,00
20	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 15,90
	<i>Media</i>	★ 29,83

Partecipazione ad Eventi Culturali 2005-2020			
Rank	Regioni	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 4,70	★ 16,67
2	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 1,70	★ 5,30
3	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 0,10	★ 0,29
4	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -0,50	★ -1,32
5	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -1,60	★ -4,12
6	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -1,10	★ -4,26
7	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -1,80	★ -5,04
8	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -1,90	★ -5,22
9	<i>Molise</i>	★ -1,90	★ -7,79
10	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ -4,50	★ -10,20
11	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -2,80	★ -10,33
12	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -3,40	★ -10,63
13	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -2,70	★ -10,93
14	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -4,20	★ -11,29
15	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -5,00	★ -12,35
16	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -4,40	★ -13,97
17	<i>Campania</i>	★ -4,20	★ -15,05
18	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -5,40	★ -15,98
19	<i>Marche</i>	★ -8,60	★ -24,23
20	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -9,20	★ -36,65
	Media	★ -2,84	★ -8,86

Declarations

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